

Oral dissolving film- A Comprehensive Review

Chakravarthi K S S*, Ilango K B, Brindha E, Jeevitha T, Kanishhari J, Thavaseelan N, Kannan R

Shree Venkateshwara College of Paramedical Science, College of Pharmacy, Erode- 638 455

Correspondence: Chakravarthi K S S, Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Shree Venkateshwara College of Paramedical Science, College of Pharmacy, Erode- 638 455.

Abstract- Oral Dissolving Film (ODFs) are thin, flexible strips that dissolve in mouth without the need for water. They were developed to overcome swallowing difficulties associated with tablets and capsules, especially in children, elderly patients, and individuals with dysphagia. These films disintegrate rapidly in saliva and provide fast drug release, leading to quicker onset of action. In some cases, drug absorption through the oral mucosa can partially avoid first pass metabolism, thereby improving bioavailability. This review discusses the structure and physiology of the buccal cavity, factors affecting buccal drug absorption, classification of oral dissolving films, formulation components, and different preparation methods such as solvent casting and hot-melt extrusion etc. It also explains important evaluation parameters, packaging consideration, and marketed products. Although oral dissolving films have some limitation, such as moisture sensitivity and limited drug loading capacity they offer many advantages including improved patient compliance, accurate dosing, conveniences, and enhanced therapeutic effectiveness. Therefore, ODFs are considered a promising and innovative drug delivery system in modern pharmaceutical science.

Keywords- Oral Dissolving film, Rapid Disintegration, First-Pass Metabolism, Method of Preparation, Evaluation parameters, Patient compliance, Novel Drug Delivery System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Oral dissolving film was developed in 1970's, based on the principles used in transdermal patch technology [1]. Many patients find difficult to swallow tablets and capsules which affects proper medication intake. About 35% of people suffer from swallowing difficulties (dysphagia). Especially, the geriatric, psychiatric, neurologically affected patient and those with conditions like stroke, Parkinson's disease swallowing can also be difficult during motion sickness or lack of water to solve this problem "Mouth dissolving film" were developed using hydrophilic polymers.

The film quickly dissolves in the mouth without water improving patient convenience and compliance [2]. The oral mucosa has a rich blood supply, allowing drugs to be absorbed directly into the blood stream without undergoing first pass metabolism. This results in improved oral bioavailability of the drug. Therefore, the oral mucosa is considered an effective site for drug delivery [3]. Fast dissolving oral films are very thin, small strips that contain the drug along with suitable excipients and dissolve quickly when placed in the mouth [4].

The primary challenges discussed in the present review are taste masking and enhancement of aqueous solubility of drugs. Pharmaceutical formulations that come into contact with the oral cavity, irrespective of the route of administration such as sublingual delivery, should possess an acceptable taste. The unpleasant taste many active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) is a major factor contributing to poor patient compliance with prescribed therapies.

Taste plays a significant role in the formulation and development of oral dosage forms, as it directly affects patient acceptability and adherence to treatment more over the Taste is an important determinant of market and commercial success of pharmaceutical product, particularly in paediatric formulation. This dosage form offers greater convenience leading to improved patient compliance and added marketing benefits oral thin film have emerged as a well-accepted technology for the systemic delivery of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and are widely used for over-the-counter (OTC) product as well as certain prescription medication [5].

II. ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF BUCCAL CAVITY

2.1 Anatomy of buccal cavity –

The oral mucosa is layered tissues the layers are

- i. *Stratified squamous epithelium*: The outer most layer
- ii. *Basement membrane and lamina propria*: The middle layer
- iii. *Submucosa*: The innermost layer [6].

(a) Oral cavity (b) Cross section oral mucosa

The epithelium as a constant cycle where new cells are produced in the basal layer and progress outward, eventually shedding from the surface. The buccal mucosa (cheek lining) is a white thick, between 40 to 50 cell layers or 500 to 800 micrometers. In contrast the mucosa of the hard/soft palates, floor of mouth and gums is thinner, around 100 to 200 micrometers thick.

The structure of the oral epithelium changes depending on its location in the mouth. Areas that face more mechanical stress, like the corners and hard palate, have a keratinized surface similar to skin, while regions such as the soft palate, floor of the mouth, and inner cheek are non-keratinized. Certain neutral lipid ceramides and acyl ceramides help in forming a protective barrier in keratinized tissue. In non-keratinized tissue, the main lipids present are cholesterol sulphate and glucosyl ceramide, which still limit water movement but allow more permeability compared to keratinized areas. Both types of oral epithelium contain a high degree of protein arranged as a filament structure with the cell layer [7].

2.2 Physiology of buccal cavity–

Buccal drug absorption mainly takes place by passive diffusion through the epithelium layer, following the concentration gradient. The major transport process involves the movement of non-ionized drug molecules across the lipid membrane of the buccal cavity. The buccal mucosa acts as a lipid-rich barrier that controls drug penetration, allowing faster absorption of suitable drugs. The rate of absorption through the buccal mucosa can be explained using a first-order kinetic process. Saliva also aids drug absorption by changing the concentration of drug present in the mouth. According to the Beard and Tom Lison relationship, a linear connection exists between salivary secretion and time, expressed by the equation.

$$-dM/dt = KC / (V_i V_t)$$

Where,

M = amount of drug present in the mouth at a given time

K = proportionality constant

V_i = the volume of solution introduced into the oral cavity

V_t = the rate of saliva secretion

C = concentration of drug in the mouth at the time [8].

III. PHYSIOLOGICAL FACTOR AFFECTING BUCCAL ABSORPTION

3.1 Epithelial permeability –

The lining of the mouth is moderately permeable more than this skin but less than the gut. The buccal mucosa itself is less permeable than the sublingual area.

3.2 Blood flow –

A dense network of blood vessels and lymphatic tissue is present allowing drugs that pass through the epithelium to enter the general circulation quickly. The blood flow rate in the buccal mucosa is about 2.4 ml/per minute per square centimetre.

3.3 Metabolic avoidance –

Drug absorbed via the oral mucosa directly into the blood stream, bypassing the initial metabolic breakdown that occurs in the liver and gut wall. This method is especially used for delivering sensitive drug like therapeutic peptides and proteins.

3.4 Saliva and Mucus –

The mouth is constantly washed by saliva, with production between 0.5 to 2liters per day. The sublingual area is exposed to a high volume of saliva, which can improve drug dissolution and increase a drug bioavailability.

3.5 Transport route and Mechanism –

Drug permeation across the epithelial barrier occurs via two main routes:

The paracellular route: The movement between adjacent epithelial cells.

The transcellular route: The movement across the actual epithelial cells, which can involve passive diffusion, carrier mediated transport and endocytic processes.

3.6 Species difference in research –

Rodents have a high keratinized epithelium which makes them unsuitable animal models for studying buccal drug delivery system [9,10]

IV. ADVANTAGES

They release the drug very quickly after placing on the tongue.

Because of their large surface area, they disintegrate and dissolve faster in the mouth.

Oral films are flexible and less fragile than tablets, so they are easier to transport, store, and handle.

They provide accurate dosing in each strip.

There is no risk of choking, since the film dissolve in saliva.

They give a pleasant mouth feel.

They help in improving patient compliance.

Since they dissolve easily and don't need water, they are suitable for patient with swallowing difficulty(dysphagia).

The medicine can be taken anytime and anywhere, making it very convenient.

They improve oral bioavailability, especially for drugs affected by first-pass metabolism.

By avoiding first-pass metabolism, the required dose is reduced, which may lower side effects.

These films are usually small in size (like a postage stamp) and dissolve on the tongue within seconds, giving a rapid drug effect [11].

V. DISADVANTAGES

These films are moisture sensitive (hygroscopic), so they must be stored in dry, so they must be stored in dry conditions. Special packaging equipment is required, and packing the films is not easy.

They need protective packing to prevent contact with water or humidity.

Large drug doses cannot be incorporated into oral films.

Eating and drinking may need to be avoided immediately after placing the film in the mouth.

Drugs that are unstable at oral (salivary) pH are not suitable for this dosage form [12].

VI. IDEAL REQUIREMENT.

The film should be thin, flexible and strong, so it doesn't break during handling.

It should be easy to manufacture and package, and convenient to use.

The film must be portable, non-sticky and should not curl or roll.

It should be easy to administer, especially for children, elderly, and uncooperative patients.

It must have a pleasant taste and good mouth feel.

It should be stable against temperature and humidity.

It should be combining the advantages of liquid medicine with the convenience of solid dosage forms.

The surface should be smooth and uniform.

It should remain physically and chemically stable and cost-effective and suitable for large-scale production [13]

VII. CLASSIFICATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING FILM

There are three main kinds of mouth dissolving film:

- i. Mucoadhesive sustained release wafer (extended-release wafer)
- ii. Mucoadhesive melt away wafer (mucoadhesive wafer)
- iii. Flash release wafer (quick release wafer [13,14])

Features	Quick Release	Mucoadhesive wafer	Mucoadhesive Extended-Release wafer
Area (cm ²)	2-8	2-7	2-4
Thickness (mm)	20-70	50-500	50-250
Structure	Single layer	Multi-Layer/Single	Multi-Layer
Excipient	Water soluble polymers	Water Soluble Polymer	Low Solubility/Insoluble Polymer
Pharmaceutical phase	Solid/Dissolved/Dispersed	Drug Molecule in Solid/Suspended	Suspension Solid/ Dissolved/ Dispersed
Application area	Lingual	Buccal or Gingival Region	Other Suitable Areas in the Gum/Oral Cavity
Dissolution	60s	Oral Consist in Minutes	8-10h maximum
Effect	Local/Systemic	Local/Systemic	Local/Systemic

VIII. FORMULATION CONSIDERATION

8.1 Drug –

The active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) is generally incorporated into a film formulation at a concentration of about 1-30% w/w. Using a micronized API improves the films feature and ensures rapid dissolution with uniform distribution throughout the fast-dissolving film. Therefore, appropriate drug loading plays a crucial role in achieving an optimal film formulation [15].

8.2 Polymer –

Hydrophilic polymer/ natural and synthetic polymer are used in oral dissolving film: -

Polymers form the main structural backbone of oral dissolving films (ODFs) and generally constitute more than 80% of the films dry weight.

Natural polymers such as pullulan starch derivation and gelatin dissolve rapidly in the oral cavity and provide a smooth mouthfeel; however, they are after brittle and therefore require plasticizers to improve flexibility.

Semi-synthetic polymers like hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) are commonly used due to their transparency good mechanical strength.

Synthetic polymer: polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) produces strong, flexible films with high tensile strength. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) forms clear and glossy films but can be brittle without plasticizers.

Synthetic polymers after better mechanical properties but dissolve more slowly.

Natural polymers dissolve faster but often need higher amount of plasticizer and excipients.

To balance dissolving rate and mechanical strength, polymer blending is widely employed in oral dissolving film formulation.

Polymer blends allow adjustment of: -

- i. Flexibility.
- ii. Disintegration and dissolution rate.
- iii. Mechanical strength.
- iv. Without requiring chemical modification of the polymers.

Proper polymer selection is essential for high quality ODFs

An ideal polymer should: -

- i. Be non-toxic and hydrophilic.
- ii. Possess good wetting and film properties.
- iii. Be chemically stable and compatible with API.
- iv. Provide adequate flexibility, peel strength and tensile strength to the film [16].

8.3 Plasticizer–

The plasticizer should be compatible with both the polymer and the solvent used in the formulation. If plasticizer are used in excess or not properly selected. They may cause defects in the film such as cracking, breaking or peeling. In addition, some plasticizer can influence the drugs absorption rate. Plasticizer containing hydroxyl groups such as polyethylene using agents like citric acid and phthalic acid esters. Diethylene glycol is also suitable for preparing films of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). Generally, plasticizer are added in concentration ranging from 0% to 20% w/w based on the dry weight of the polymer [17].

8.4 Flavouring agent –

Flavouring agents may be selected from synthetic aromatic substances, oleoresins or natural extracts obtained from plants such as leaves, fruits and flowers. These flavours can be used individually or in suitable combination. A wide variety of flavours can be incorporated into the formulation including menthol derivatives and essential oils. Commonly used flavour strong minty agent such as peppermint, spearmint, wintergreen, cinnamon and clove as well as citrus flavours like lemon and orange. Sweet flavouring options such as vanillin, vanilla, chocolate and fruits essence including apple, raspberry, cherry and pineapple are also employed. The quantity of flavouring agent required to effectively mask the unpleasant taste of the drug depends on the nature and intensity of the selected flavours [18].

8.5 Sweetening agent –

Sweetening agents play a vital role in pharmaceutical formulation that is designed or disintegrate in the oral cavity, as they improve palatability and patient compliance. Traditionally, sugar such as, dextrose, fructose, glucose, and liquid glucose have been used as sweeteners. However, artificial sweeteners are now widely preferred in pharmaceutical preparation due to their high sweetness intensity and low caloric value. Saccharin cyclamate and aspartame are classified as first generation artificial sweeteners, while acesulfame-k, sucralose and neotame belong to the second generation of artificial sweeteners [18].

8.6 Surfactants –

These agents enhance the wettability of the film, promote better drug solubilization and support faster dissolution. As a result, they help achieve uniform drug distribution and improved bioavailability examples included Tween 80, Span 60, and Poloxamer [19].

8.7 Saliva stimulating agent –

Oral thin film (OTFs) breakdown immediately when they meet saliva in the oral cavity.

Saliva stimulating agents enhance saliva secretion, which in turn supports rapid disintegration and dissolution of the film. The increased flow of saliva accelerates the breakdown of the film and improves the dissolution rate of the drug. These agents are typically incorporated at a concentration of about 2-6% w/w of the film and may be used individually or in combination. Common examples include citric acid, lactic acid and ascorbic acid [20].

IX. METHOD OF PREPARATION

- 9.1 Solvent casting method
- 9.2 Hot melt extrusion method
- 9.3 Rolling method
- 9.4 Solid dispersion method
- 9.5 Semi solid casting method

9.1 Solvent casting method –

This is the oldest method of preparation of sublingual film.

Polymer is dissolved in suitable vehicle (beaker)

Drug and other additives are dissolved in suitable solvent (beaker)

Now both the solutions are mixed and stirred for a specified time.

Then the solution is sonicated for avoidance of air bubbles

This solution is poured into the petri dish and kept in an oven throughout the night at 50-60°C for drying.

Peel off the film and keep it in a desiccator till further application [21].

(c) Solvent casting method

9.2 Hot melt extrusive method –

Hot melt extrusion (HME) involves feeding materials, melting them through heat and shear, and then shaping the resulting mass. Feeding methods include float-feeding, controlled by screw speed and starve-feeding, controlled by an external feeder, with the later often preferred for uniformity and reduced stress on the machine. After melting, the material is shaped using a die, with the final product quality influenced by the die design, cooling, processing conditions. Hot melt extrusion method is classified into two types [22].

9.2.1 Single screw extruder

9.2.2 Twin screw extruder

(d) Hot melt extrusion

9.3 Rolling method –

In the rolling method, liquid medication either a solution or a suspension and spread it on to carrier using rollers. The process typically uses water or a water-alcohol mix as a solvent. Once this liquid layer dries on the rollers, simply cut the resulting film into the sizes you need. To get the mixture right, you use a high-shear processor to dissolve the active ingredients and other components into a small amount of water. Finally, water-soluble hydrocolloids are mixed into transform that liquid into a smooth, thick (viscous) solution [21].

(e) Rolling method

9.4 Solid dispersion method –

Solid dispersion is a technique where a hydrophilic (water insoluble) drug is distributed within a hydrophilic (water loving) carrier or matrix. This matrix can be structured (crystalline) or unstructured (amorphous). Based on ingredients.

9.4.1 Binary – A simple two ingredient mix of the drug and a polymer.

9.4.2 Ternary – A three ingredient mix (drug + polymer + surfactant) to help things blend.

9.4.3 Surface – Uses specific polymers / copolymers, often melted together, to help the drug speed out dissolve faster [23].

9.5 Semisolid casting method –

This method involves preparing a stable solution with a specific minimum solid content and viscosity. The process step involves.

9.5.1. *Preparing a primary solution*—A water soluble film forming polymer solution is made.

9.5.2 *Adding an insoluble polymer* – This solution is combined with an acid insoluble polymer solution (like cellulose acetate phthalate or butyrate) to form a gel mass.

9.5.3 *Incorporating a plasticizer* – An appropriate amount of plasticizer is added to the gel mass.

9.5.4 *Casting the film* – The resulting gel is cast into the films or ribbons using controlled heat drums [30].

X. EVALUATION PARAMETERS

10.1 Weight variation –

The mouth dissolving oral film were weighed using an analytical balance, and an average weight of each film was determined. Maintaining uniform weight among the films is important uniform because it ensures that each film contain the correct amount of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and other required excipients.

10.2 Weight uniformity –

The cast film was cut into pieces from different location, and each film was weighed using an electronic balance the average weight was then calculated.

10.3 Thickness –

The thickness of the film is measured using a micrometre screw gauge at a minimum of five different strategic locations. This measurement is important to ensure uniform thickness, which is directly related to the accuracy of dose in the film.

10.4 Dryness test –

Eight stages of film drying have been identified: Set to touch, dust-free, tack-free (surface dry), dry-to-touch, dry hard, dry through (dry to handle), dry to recoat and dry print-free. Track refers to tenacity with the film adheres to accessory, such as piece of paper, when pressed into conduct with the film instrument are also available to study this property.

10.5 Tensile strength –

Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied at point where the film specimen breaks. It is calculated by dividing the load at rupture by the cross-sectional area of the film, as shown in the equation below:

$$\text{Tensile strength} = (\text{load at failure} * 100) / (\text{film thickness} * \text{film width})$$

10.6 Surface PH –

A 4-centimetre square portion of the film was cut and placed in distilled water in a glass tube for one hour to allow swelling for surface Ph measurement the combined glass electrode of pH meter was then position near the surface of the film and allowed to acclimatize for 1 minute before recording surface ph. The average value from threereplicated experiment was recorded.

10.7 Folding endurance –

Folding endurance was determined by repeatedly folding the film at the same position until it broke. The folding endurance value refers to the number of times the film can be folded without breaking.

10.8 Tear resistance –

The tear resistance of the plastic film or sheeting is a complex function related to its ultimate rupture strength. It is determined by measuring the force required to initiate tearing at a very low loading rate of 51mm (2 inch) per minute. Tear resistant is expressed in newton (or pounds-forces) and indicates the maximum force of stress usually observed beginning of tearing, that is required to tear the specimen.

10.9 Percentage elongation –

When the stress is applied, the film sample stretched, which is known as strain. Strain is defined as the deformation of the film divided by the original dimension of the sample percentage elongation is calculate as the increases in the length divided by the original length multiplied by hundred.

10.10 Drug content uniformity –

Uniformity ensure consistency is the medication content. The drug content of all batches was determined using random sampling. The FDF (22cm²) was dissolved in phosphate buffer, and the resulting mixture was filtered before being introduced into the HPLC. The drug content was calculated based on the average of the three measurements.

10.11 Stability testing –

The stability testing is performed by storing the oral films is stability chamber under controlled condition at 25°C with 60% humidity and at 40°C with 75% humidity for up to 12 months, in accordance with ICH guidelines during the period. Various properties such as thickness, appearance, strength moisture content, and dissolution behaviour are evaluated.

10.12 Disintegration time –

The disintegration time limit of 30 seconds or less specified for orally disintegrating tablets in CDER guidance can also be applied to fast dissolving oral film. Although no official guidelines exist for oral fast disintegrating film, the limit may be used qualitative guideline during the development stage or for quality control test. The pharmacopeial disintegration test apparatus can be used to perform this study. The typical disintegration time for film ranges from 5-30 seconds.

10.13 Dissolution test –

Dissolution testing is performed using a standard basket or paddle apparatus as specified in pharmacopeia. The dissolution medium is selected according to the condition required for drug solubility and the highest dose for the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API). In some cases, testing becomes difficult because the film strip may float on the surface of liquid when the paddle apparatus is used.

10.14 Invitro dissolution studies –

As in vitro dissolution Study for selected film formulation was carried out for 3 minutes using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions the dissolution medium was maintained at 37± 0.5 °c and stirred at 50 rpm. Samples of 5 ml were withdrawn at 80 seconds intervals and replaced with an equal volume of fresh pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solution. The withdrawn samples were further diluted to 1 ml in volumetric flask. The drug concentration in samples was determined using UV spectrophotometer at a maximum wavelength of 256nm with an electroplate Ltd dissolution apparatus. The enhanced dissolution rate may be attributed to the significantly increased surface area of drug available for dissolution.

10.15 Contact angle –

The contact angle can be measured at 37 °C using a goniometer (AB Lorentz and wetter, Germany) this is done by placing a drop of distilled water on surface of dry film. Images of the water droplet are captured using a digital camera within 10 seconds after deposition. The contact angle is measured both sides of the droplet, and the average value calculated [23,24,25,26,27].

XI. PACKING OF ORAL DISSOLVING FILM

The effectiveness, storage life, and production of these oral dosage forms heavily on proper packaging. Key features include:

11.1 Moisture protection - Barrier films are specifically used for medication that is sensitive to moisture.

11.2 Information display -Primary packaging, particularly sealing pouches developed with LABTECH GMBH technology, offers sample space for essential information like logos, direction and codes.

11.3 Code efficiency-The expense of packaging this film, which is created via a laminating process, is comparable to that of traditional tablets.

XII. PACKAGING CONSERADATION

The material chosen for packing must meet several critical criteria:

12.1 Safety standard – These must be non-toxic, safe for consumption related use, and have FDA approval.

12.2 Neutral properties – The packaging should be non-reactive and possess no taste or odour that could transfer to the film.

12.3 Environmental properties – It must resist appropriated temperature ranges and include necessary feature like instruments and bar codes [31].

XIII. TYPES OF PACKAGING

13.1 Pouches (Foil, paper, plastic) –

Pouches provide robust, temper resistance and protect the product from environmental factors such as moisture, light and air. Their flexible design allows for efficient sealing using standard vertical or horizontal equipment.

13.2 Single pouches –

Designed to be peel able for user convenience with “quick dissolve” films. Feature high barrier protection, typically combining a clear side with a foil side to block gas and moisture effectively.

13.3 Multi-unit blister cards –

Comprised of a plastic blister that holds the film and an aluminium lid that seals it. The manufacturing processes involves heating and vacuum forming a thermoplastic sheet into a mould before the product is placed inside and heat sealed [24].

XIV. PATENT AND MARKET PRODUCT

Country	Patent number	Title	Inventors
US	20110305768A1	Quick dissolving oral thin film for targeted delivery of therapeutic agents.	Hai-Quan Mao
WO	2012103464A2	Oral thin film vaccine preparation	Brian Pulliam

EP	1680079A2	Rapidly disintegrating films for delivery of pharmaceutical and cosmetic agents.	Scott D Bamhart
US	5948430	Water-soluble film for oral.	Zerbe
WO	2014183054A1	Thin film with a high load of active ingredient.	Eric Allen
EP	2509631A4	Ph sensitive compounds in taste masking within oral thin film strip.	A MarkSchobel
US	164871B2	A fast-dissolving oral consumable film containing taste masking agent.	Bess
US	7347985B2	Breath freshening and oral cleaning product with a magnolia bark extract.	Maxwell
WO	2013085224A1	Bitter taste masked oral thin film formulation of Sildenafil citrate.	Dae-Kun Song
US	6159498	Bio erodiblefilm for delivery of pharmaceutical compound of the mucosal surface.	Tappolsky

Table 1: List of patented oral dissolving film [28].

Product Name	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient	Indication	Manufacturer
Benadryl allergy quick dissolve strips	Diphenhydramine HCL (25mg)	Allergic symptoms	McNeil-PPC, Inc., Fort Washington, PA, USA.
Triaminic children's thin strips	Dextromethorphan (3.67mg) and phenylephrineHCL (2.5mg)	Cough suppressant and nasal decongestant	Novartis Consumer Health, Basel, Switzerland.
Gas-X thin strips	Simethicone (62.5mg)	Anti flatulent	Novartis Consumer Health, Basel, Switzerland
Padia-Lax quick dissolve strips	Sennosides (8.6mg)	Occasional constipation	C.B. Fleer Company, Lynchburg, VA, USA
Zolmitriptan ODF	Zolmitriptan (2.5mg)	Migraine	APR Applied Pharma research and Laptec, Balerna, Switzerland
Sildenafil Sandoz Oro dispersible film	Sildenafil (25/50/100 mg)	Erectile dysfunction	Sandoz, Basel, Switzerland
Risperidone HEXAL SF Schmelz film	Risperidone (5mg)	Schizophrenia	Hexal AG, Holz Kirchen, Germany
Levocetirizine orally disintegrating strips	Levocetirizine (5mg)	Allergic symptoms	D.K. Livkon Healthcare Pvt.Ltd., Mumbai, India.
Vitamin D3 Oral Disintegrating strips.	Vitamin D3 (6000 IU)	Vitamin D3 supplement	D.K. Livkon Healthcare Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India.
Listerine Pocked Pak	Pullulan, Xanthan	Mouth freshener	Johnson and Johnson

breath strips	menthol, salicylate, thymol, succinate	methyl eucalyptol, methyl	Consumer Health Inc., New Brunswick, NJ, USA.
---------------	---	---------------------------------	---

Table 2: Marketed product of oral dissolving film [29].

XV. CONCLUSION

Oral dissolving film (ODF) is also known as mouth dissolving or fast dissolving oral films, or innovative drug delivery system in pharmaceutical science. Compared to conventional oral dosage form, these films offers better patient acceptance and compliances due to their ease of administration rapid disintegration, and absences of choking risk.

The main purpose of developing (ODF) was to address swallowing difficulty associated with tablets and capsules, particularly in paediatric and geriatric, psychiatric, dysphagic patient. These films dissolve quickly in the oral cavity without the need for water, making them highly convenient and suitable for patient who have difficulty in swallowing.

Rapid disintegration and dissolution in saliva resulting faster drug release and onset of action. Partial absorption through the oral mucosa helps in hepatic first pass metabolism, thereby improving bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. ODF used in the treatment of various condition such as pain, allergy, hypertension.

Overall, mouth dissolving film provide precise dosing, improve safety, enhanced therapeutics response and high patient compliant, making them promising alternative to conventional dosage forms.

REFERENCES

- [1]Jadhav vidya, “A brief review on mouth dissolving film”, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical research application*, pp. 1079-1084, 2022.
- [2] Yogeeta O Agarwal, “Development, Optimization and characterization of hydrocolloid-based mouth dissolving film”, *Food hydrocolloids for health*, pp. 1-2, 2022.
- [3] Anil M Pethe, “Formulation, Optimization and Evaluation of Mouth dissolving film of nifedipine by using design of experiment”, *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical science*, pp.331-343,2016.
- [4]Ye Huang, Jianwei Wang, “Study on dexamethasone fast dissolving oral film based on pullulan -Vitamin E Succinate”, *Journal of radiation research and applied science*, pp.1-10,2025.
- [5]Quazi Bilal, “Review on mouth dissolving film”, *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, pp.232-238, 2020.
- [6] Reen Sheoran, “Buccal drug delivery system: A review”, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical science*, pp. 40-46, 2018.
- [7] Amir H. Shojaei, “Buccal mucosa as a route for systemic drug delivery: A review”, *J Pharm Pharmaceutical Science*, pp. 15-30, 1998.
- [8] N. G. Raghavendra Rao, B. Shravani, Mettu Srikanth Reddy, “Overview on Buccal Drug Delivery Systems”, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research*, pp. 80-88, 2013.
- [9]Hezam Saleh Mohammed Dhaifalla, “Review on buccal drug delivery system”, *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, pp. 1-11, 2024.
- [10] Arushi Saxena, “Oral dissolving film: A comprehensive review”, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, pp. 139-147, 2022.

- [11]Mital S. Panchal, "Formulation and evaluation of mouth dissolving film of ropinirole hydrochloride by using pullulan polymers", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Allied Sciences*, pp.60-72, 2012.
- [12] Sayali Kokate, "Mouth dissolving film: innovation in formulation and technology", *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research*, pp. 492-505, 2022.
- [13] Samidha Sonkamble, "A Review on Mouth Dissolving Film", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science*, pp. 4321-4237, 2025.
- [14] Emrah OZAKAR, "Current overview of oral thin films", *Turk Journal of Pharmaceutical Science*, pp.111-121, 2021.
- [15] Pawan S. Avhad, "Review on: Recent advance in mouth dissolving film", *International journal of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis*, pp. 163-168, 2022.
- [16] Niharika Lal, "Therapeutic potential and formulation considerations of orally disintegrating films in acute disorders", *Discovered Pharmaceutical Science*, pp. 1-54, 2025.
- [17] Balwant Singh Rawat, "A review on Oro dispersible film based novel drug delivery system", *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, pp. 3480-3488, 2024.
- [18] Ankita P. Chaudhari, Bhagayshri A. Patil, S.A. Tadavi, Dr.S.P. Pawar, "Mouth dissolving film: An Innovative and Effective Drug Delivery system", *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Allied Sciences*, pp. 78-89, 2023.
- [19] Nikita Sanjay Suryawanshi, Sakshi Sachin Ghag, Sharmeen Mohd. Anis Shaikh, "Mouth dissolving films, A Revolutionary Drug Delivery System", *Journal of emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, pp. 772-780, 2021.
- [20] Nilesh S. Kulkarni, "A Systemic review on oral drug delivery as fast dissolving film to improve therapeutic effectiveness", *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, pp. 1771-1778, 2021.
- [21] Satish Chavan, "Fast dissolving oral films, various formulation, Methodologies, Evaluation and Current approach", *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research*, pp. 290-301, 2022.
- [22] Mahalakshmi Rathanand, "Hot Melt Extrusion Technique: A novel continuous manufacturing method for enteric-coated pellets", *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, pp. 13-19, 2021.
- [23] Diksha Thakur, "Solid dispersion of novel approach for enhancement of solubility and dissolution rate: A review", *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research*, pp. 7-14, 2019.
- [24] Nishant. P. Deshmukh, "Formulation and evaluation of oral fast dissolving films", *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, pp. 186-197, 2025.
- [25] Ashwini B. Pote, "A review on: Fast dissolving oral thin film", *International Journal in Pharmaceutical Science*, pp. 474-481, 2023.
- [26] K. Sunil Kumar Reddy, "A detailed review on fast dissolving oral films", *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, pp. 1315-1326, 2018.
- [27] Gagan G, "A review on oral disintegrating films: A novel drug delivery system", *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, pp. 121-137, 2025.
- [28] Umashankar M. S, "Recent update on oral film: A bench to market potential", *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, pp. 27-33, 2018.
- [29] Shrey Jacob, "Oro dispersible films: Current innovation and emerging trends", *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, pp. 2-41, 2023.

[30] Nishi Thakur, "Overview: A novel approach of fast dissolving films and their patients", *Advances in Biological Research*, pp. 50-58, 2013.

[31] Komal A Kawale, "A review on fast dissolving oral film", *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, pp. 7-17, 2023.